

Growth Performance and Nutrient Utilization of Weaned Rabbits Fed With Diets in Which Palm Kernel Cake (PKC) was Replaced with Cooked Tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) Seed Meal

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ABSTRACT

A feeding trial was conducted on 30 weaned rabbits of New Zealand and Chinchilla crossbreeds aged 5-6 weeks with an initial average weight of 716g on their growth performance and nutrient digestibility. The rabbits were divided into 5 groups and randomly allotted to 5 dietary treatments, A, B, C, D and E, formulated with Palm kernel (*Elaeis guineensis*) cake replaced with Cooked Tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) Seed Meal (CTSM) at 0, 25, 50,75 and 100% respectively. The rabbits were fed *ad-libitum*. The average body weight, body weight gain and feed conversion ratio showed no significant differences ($P>0.05$). While the values of feed intake and digestibility were significantly ($P<0.05$) affected by the dietary treatments. The results suggest that Cooked Tallow Seed Meal can be used to replace PKC at 100% in the diets of Rabbits.

KEYWORDS: Rabbits, Palm Kernel Cake (PKC), Tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*), Growth, Nutrient Digestibility

INTRODUCTION:

The past few years have witnessed a rapid growth in the population of developing countries including Nigeria with resultant increase in the demand for protein of animal origin. Meanwhile, increasing the production of animal protein at a reasonable cost to enhance the diet quality of the populace has been part of the objectives of the National Agriculture policy of Nigeria. The potential of rabbit production in alleviating the low animal protein intake in Nigeria and other developing countries especially those in the tropics needs no emphasis (Amaefule *et al.*, 2005). More so, there are no religious edicts preventing their production and consumption unlike pigs (Ayuk *et al.*, 2009). Feed supply has remained a major constraint in animal production due to increasing cost of conventional feed stuffs brought about by the competition between man and animal for protein sources (Amaefule *et al.*, 2004). Hence the need to search for alternative protein sources that are cheap, readily available and less competed for by man and industries (Akinmutimi, 2007). This has led to the study using legumes forage seed such as Tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) as source of protein to replace palm kernel cake (*Elaeis guineensis*). However, its utilization is limited by the presence of some anti-nutritional factors (ANF) such as tannins, phytate, hydrogen cyanide and saponins (Anhwange *et al.*, 2004). Processing by heating, cooking and fermentation are effective ways of eliminating undesirable anti-nutritional factors (ANF). Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effects of replacing Palm kernel (*Elaeis guineensis*) cake with cooked tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) seed meal, on the growth and nutrient digestibility of weaned rabbits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thirty weaned rabbits aged 5-6 weeks, having an average weight of 716g were used for this experiment. The unsexed animals which were of New Zealand and Chinchilla crossbreed were kept in the Teaching and Research farm of School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. The raw tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) seed was sorted to ensure homogeneity of product. The tallow was cleaned and poured into an aluminium pot containing 15 litres of water. The tallow seed was allowed to cook at 100°C for two hours according to the methods described by Kaankuka *et al.* (1996) in order to remove the anti-nutritional factors (ANFs). It was dried and milled using locally fabricated miller. The milled samples were kept in air tight bags ready for use. The rabbits were randomly allotted to five dietary treatments A, B, C, D and E, formulated with Palm kernel (*Elaeis guineensis*) cake replaced with CTSM at 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100% levels respectively (Table 1). They were housed in pens partitioned with wire mesh; feed and water were supplied *ad-libitum*. Daily feed intake (g), average body weight gain (g) and feed conversion ratio were monitored. At the end of 8th week of the experiment, 3 rabbits were randomly selected and transferred to individual metabolic cages for metabolic studies which lasted for 5 days. Faecal outputs were collected from the selected animals and weighed fresh for the period of the 5 days. Samples of the faeces were oven dried at 80°C to constant weight and later analysed for proximate constituents. These records were used to determine digestibility of the feed nutrients by the rabbits.

Data collected were subjected to one way analysis of variance using the SAS system (1998). Means were separated by Duncan's multiple range tests (1995).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the percentage composition of experimental diets.

Table 1: Composition of experimental diets

Ingredients	A	B	C	D	E
Maize	58.77	58.77	58.77	58.77	58.77
PKC	24.18	18.14	12.09	6.05	0.00
CTSM	0.00	6.05	12.09	18.14	24.18
Rice offal	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Oyster shell	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Premix	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Blood meal	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Methronine	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15
Coccidiostat	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Proximate composition					
Dry matter (%)	94.20	93.80	94.40	92.80	93.20
Crude protein (%)	17.16	15.73	19.26	15.26	19.26
Crude fibre (%)	13.40	15.80	20.80	10.60	14.40
Ash (%)	12.50	13.50	14.00	14.00	13.00
Ether extract (%)	11.00	16.00	16.00	17.00	14.00
NFE (%)	45.94	39.00	29.94	43.14	39.34

A, B, C, D and E = Diets containing 100%:0%, 75:25%, 50:50%, 25:75% and 0:100% Palm kernel cake: CTSM respectively.

CTSM- Cooked Tallow Seed Meal

The proximate composition of all the experimental diets fell within the range recommended for growth of weaned rabbits (Lebas *et al.*, 1986). The values of the crude protein (CP), 15.73%, 19.26%, 15.26% and 19.26% in the experimental diets which contained CTSM: B, C, D and E respectively, suggests that the feedstuff is a good source of protein. The performance parameters of the experimental animals are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance of weaned rabbits fed Palm kernel (*Elaeis guineensis*) cake replaced with CTSM.

Parameters	A	B	C	D	E	SEM	SL
Av. initial body wt (g)	725.00	775.00	716.66	716.66	666.66	15.46	NS
Av. final body wt (g)	1082.50	1070.41	1024.37	1031.25	1104.00	317.74	NS
Av. body wt gain (g)	74.58	69.79	54.37	64.5	89.58	5.19	NS
Av. feed intake (g)	58.82 ^{ab}	66.30 ^a	54.56 ^b	56.84 ^b	61.50 ^{ab}	1.32	*
Feed conversion ratio	1.27	1.37	1.57	1.60	1.30	0.11	NS

a, b = means denoted by different superscript are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different

SL= Significant level; NS = Not significant ($P > 0.05$)

SEM= Standard error mean

Treatment effects were not significant ($P > 0.05$) for: final body weight (FBW), body weight gain (BWG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR) which indicates a possible elimination or reduction of antinutritional factors in CTSM due to the cooking process as reported by Udedibie (1991) and Umar *et al.* (2007). However, the significant ($P < 0.05$) differences observed in the values of average feed intake (AFI) with rabbits in Treatment B having the highest feed intake 66.30g, could be as a result of high distinctive flavour by tallow (*Detarium*

microcarpum) which is in line with the report of McDonald *et al.* (1988). The digestibility for all the nutrients presented in Table 3, i.e. dry matter, crude protein, crude fibre, ether extract, ash and nitrogen were relatively good which ranged from 62.83% to 89.33% but revealed significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3: Nutrient digestibility (%) of weaned rabbits fed Palm kernel (*Elaeis guineensis*) cake replaced with CTSM.

Parameters	A	B	C	D	E
Dry matter	80.70±145 ^a	76.31±5.38 ^a	69.38±2.63 ^b	72.21±1.52 ^a	77.80±3.76 ^a *
Crude protein	82.08±1.35 ^b	83.95±0.32 ^a	77.01±1.97 ^c	79.82±1.5 ^c	83.62±2.80 ^a *
Crude fibre	67.07±0.96 ^a	67.71±7.41 ^a	66.79±2.85 ^a	58.51±5.1 ^b	68.69±5.27 ^a *
Ether extract	68.68±1.25 ^b	74.68±5.80 ^a	65.62±2.95 ^b	69.43±1.76 ^{ab}	74.17±2.04 ^a *
Ash	72.27±0.89 ^c	80.73±0.90 ^b	81.44±1.60 ^b	83.29±1.26 ^b	87.52±2.14 ^a *
NFE	89.33±0.80 ^a	76.62±5.36 ^b	62.83±3.20 ^c	85.06±1.12 ^a	84.06±2.57 ^a *

Means with different superscripts on the same row are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different.

SL= Significant level; *=significant ($P < 0.05$)

The good nutrient digestibility observed is in line with Hannah *et al.* (1991) who reported that protein supplementation improves nutrient digestibility.

CONCLUSION

The results from the research have shown that cooked Tallow (*Detarium microcarpum*) seed meal can be used in the diets of rabbits as a protein source at 100% without any deleterious effect on the performance of rabbits.

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